

A Study of Multiple Intelligence on Students' Achievements of Students Studying at Secondary Level

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Abstract

In India, secondary school students' academic success is significantly influenced by the theory of multiple intelligences. Their success may be significantly impacted by the identification and development of diverse intelligences that go beyond academics. Recognising multiple intelligences such as linguistic, logical-mathematical, musical, interpersonal, intrapersonal, and more can cater to a wider range of students in India's competitive educational environment, where rote learning frequently predominates. Teachers can more effectively engage pupils, encourage holistic development, and boost performance by adapting their teaching strategies to these different intelligences. Students are encouraged to pursue their individual abilities and interests when various intelligences are acknowledged and nurtured, which improves motivation and self-esteem. By offering secondary-level students in India a more inclusive and diverse educational experience that takes into account their unique talents and potential, embracing the idea of multiple intelligences can improve their academic performance. The researcher had conducted the study survey with the help of a structured questionnaire on 216 respondents from education sector to know the role and effect of Multiple Intelligence on Students' Achievements of Students Studying at Secondary Level and concludes that there is significant effect of Multiple Intelligence on Students' Achievements.

Keywords: Multiple Intelligences (MI), Secondary School Students, Academic Success, Educational Environment, Teaching Strategies, Holistic Development, Motivation and Self-Esteem.

Introduction

Knowledge of the intricate structure of intelligence is now crucial for fostering students' success in education, which is a dynamic journey. In this regard, Howard Gardner's work on multiple intelligences (MI) has fundamentally altered how individuals view and approach learning. Instead than following a one-size-fits-all paradigm, MI acknowledges that people have a wide variety of intelligences, each of which influences their own learning methods, talents, and abilities. It acknowledges that secondary education is a crucial stage in students' academic development and, more crucially, in their preparation for life after school. In this vital stage, recognising the existence and importance of different intelligences can significantly impact students' educational experiences. Sener and Cokcaliskan (2018) looked at the relationship between Multiple Intelligences (MI) and learning preferences among Indian secondary school students. Students displayed a range of MI profiles, including linguistic, logical-mathematical, bodily-kinaesthetic, and other types. Their learning styles were consequently influenced by these various intelligences. For instance, pupils with high linguistic intelligence tended to favour text-based instruction, whereas those with high bodily-kinaesthetic intelligence favoured hands-on, experiential learning methods. The necessity for Indian educators to acknowledge these personal variations and modify their teaching strategies was brought home by this. By doing this, teachers could

increase student engagement and help them have a more thorough learning experience that takes into consideration their individual MI profiles.

Julius and Evans (2015) addressed the relationship between knowledge practises and academic accomplishment in the setting of Higher Secondary School in India, building on this basis. They emphasized the link between better academic achievement and efficient study methods. In a way, adding the Multiple Intelligences theory to this highlighted how a student's particular intelligences can influence their preferred study techniques. Students with strong logical and mathematical aptitude, for instance, might do well in structured problem-solving situations, but those with great interpersonal aptitude might do well in group study situations. The success of students can be greatly impacted by identifying these intelligences and combining them with specialized study techniques.

Furthermore, Nayak (2018) examined how Smartphone use, addiction, and academic performance interact in complex ways among Indian students enrolled in higher education. Gender's moderating influence was investigated in this situation. The MI framework makes it clear that various intelligences may affect students' propensity for Smartphone addiction and their capacity to handle academic duties. The negative impacts of Smartphone addiction on students' academic performance may be lessened in people with high intrapersonal intelligence due to their ability for better self-regulation. In order to create effective

learning settings that meet both the problems given by contemporary technology and MI diversity, it is imperative for educators and policymakers to be aware of these differences in the secondary school scene in India.

Literature Review

The idea of "Multiple Intelligence" (MI), popularized by Howard Gardner, has irrevocably changed practice and education. It asserts that there is a spectrum of intelligences that people can have, including linguistic, logical-mathematical, interpersonal, and intrapersonal intelligences. Investigating MI's complex dynamics is necessary to comprehend how it influences the accomplishments of secondary-level pupils in India. According to MacCann et al. (2020), emotional intelligence has a considerable influence on academic performance and is closely related to interpersonal intelligence. The ability to navigate social complexities, control stress, and channel emotions for productive learning is provided to pupils through emotional intelligence. This emphasized the value of cultivating interpersonal intelligence in secondary-level Indian kids, not just to support academic ability but also to foster resilience for surviving in a globally interconnected environment.

Kpolovie et al. (2014) emphasized the holistic aspect of academic performance by focusing on the predictive influence of enthusiasm in learning and attitudes towards school. While MI highlights the variety of intelligences, it's also important to understand how students' attitudes and interests interact with their cognitive abilities. Although a student with a strong musical intelligence may do well in music-related disciplines, their overall success depends on how they approach other subjects. Teachers can customize their pedagogical techniques and create more welcoming learning environments for secondary-level students across India by acknowledging these intersections between MI, interests, and attitudes. In India, socioeconomic conditions and educational environments also shape students' performance at the secondary level. It's critical to understand how outside influences, such as students' school preferences, shape their educational experiences.

Singh (2015) focused on private schools in urban and rural settings, while MI focuses on individual cognitive aptitudes. Private schools may better suit pupils' varied intelligences because they frequently have more resources and cutting-edge teaching techniques. However, the accessibility of such institutions differs between geographical areas and socioeconomic levels, having an impact on secondary students' academic progress. In order to properly evaluate student accomplishment in the Indian context, it is crucial to place MI within the

larger framework of educational inequities and opportunities.

Roth et al. (2015) looked at the relationship between "intelligence" and academic performance. Their meta-analysis revealed that "intelligence," while unquestionably influential, is not the only factor that determines academic performance. In India, it becomes crucial to recognise and foster the many "intelligences" of secondary-level students. Recognising a student's strong "interpersonal intelligence" could encourage collaborative learning opportunities and possibly boost their overall achievement. A thorough path to student success is thus provided by incorporating the MI tenets into educational practices. Beyond "intelligence," the involvement of secondary-level pupils in their academic endeavours appears as a critical factor in their success. In his research, Lee (2014) assessed the complex relationship between student engagement and academic success. The importance of students' active involvement in the learning process is highlighted in this perspective, which complements the MI. While students' degrees of engagement have a significant impact on how well they use these cognitive abilities, while they may have various "intelligences," they do. For example, a motivated student who exhibits strong "linguistic intelligence" and excels in writing and communication, realizing their potential and achieving real academic success. This emphasized how crucial it is to design engaging and dynamic learning environments that take into account the various skills and requirements of students within India's secondary education system.

Interventions going beyond traditional educational approaches have gained appeal in India's quest to improve student achievement at the secondary level. Maynard et al. (2017) assessed how "mindfulness-based interventions" can improve students' cognition, academic performance, behaviour, and socio-emotional functioning. By offering "mindfulness" as a comprehensive path for student growth, this complemented the MI framework. By improving focus, emotional control, and self-awareness, "mindfulness" techniques assist pupils in efficiently using their "intelligences." By incorporating such interventions into the educational system, teachers in India have the chance to give pupils the means to maximise their variety of "intelligences," fostering both academic excellence and personal development.

According to Alam (2020), the introduction of "Artificial Intelligence" (AI) into India's educational system in recent years has created new "possibilities and challenges" for improving student achievement, particularly at the secondary level. The way we support "Multiple Intelligences" (MI) could undergo a revolution as a result of the junction

of AI and education. As to the primary concept of the MI, educational content may be tailored to each student's strengths and shortcomings using AI-driven adaptive learning platforms. The effects of "learning strategy instruction," which focuses on how students' learning styles can affect their academic performance, was looked at extensively by Donker et al. (2014). They emphasized the significance of understanding that "intelligence is not a fixed trait" but rather a flexible quality. Recognising and fostering these different intelligences through specialized "learning strategies" might greatly improve academic achievement in the setting of secondary-level pupils in India.

In India, where educational systems have historically placed a strong emphasis on "linguistic and logical-mathematical intelligences," Stump et al. (2014) emphasized on how students' opinions of their own cognitive abilities can impact their academic journeys. Recognising and encouraging other intelligences, such as spatial or intrapersonal, can be helpful in enhancing and diversifying students' learning experiences at the secondary level. A more holistic approach to education can help students in India's secondary schools achieve well-rounded success by placing an emphasis on the development of these intelligences in addition to traditional academics. The significance of anticipating academic success in higher education was highlighted by Alyahyan and Dustegor (2020). This calls for acknowledging the various intelligences that students in India bring to the table. As to the MI, people have a variety of intelligences, including linguistic, logical-mathematical, and interpersonal ones. The academic success of kids can be greatly impacted by effectively utilizing these intelligences.

Masino and Nino-Zarazua (2016) focussed on methods for raising student learning standards, especially in developing nations. Understanding how treatments mesh with Multiple Intelligences will be helpful for India's broad and diversified educational system. It is important to take into account the wider spectrum, even if conventional techniques have frequently concentrated on language and logical-mathematical intelligences. Interactive learning techniques, for instance, can improve comprehension and retention by incorporating visual and spatial intelligences. In

addition, emphasizing the value of interpersonal and intrapersonal intelligences helps promote cooperative and emotionally supportive learning settings, raising student accomplishment levels even further. According to O'Malley et al. (2015), home structure and school atmosphere are just two of the many variables that affect students' academic performance. Understanding how these elements interact with Multiple Intelligences is essential in the context of secondary education in India. An environment that is conducive to learning can be fostered by a welcoming school culture that acknowledges and supports different intelligences. Also important comprehends how a student's household environment affects their ability to acquire intelligence. For example, a child's academic journey may be greatly aided by parental support and encouragement of their special intellect. For educators and policymakers aiming to maximize the accomplishments of secondary-level students, taking into account their unique abilities and circumstances, it is imperative that they recognise these moderating impacts within India's educational landscape.

Objective

1. To know the role of Multiple Intelligence on Students' Achievements of Students Studying at Secondary Level.
2. To know the effect of Multiple Intelligence on Students' Achievements.

Methodology

The researcher had conducted the study survey with the help of a structured questionnaire on 216 respondents from education sector to know the role and effect of Multiple Intelligence on Students' Achievements of Students Studying at Secondary Level. The primary data is collected through "random sampling method" and data was analyzed by "mean and t-test."

Findings

Respondent's general details are shared in the table below where in 216 respondents, males are 64.4% and females are 35.6%. 34.7% are below 40 years of age, 43.1% comes in the category of 40-45 years of age group and 22.2% are above 45 years of age. 37.5% of them are working from less than 5 years, 34.7% are there in their field from last 5-8 years and rest 27.8% are working from more than 8 years.

Table 1 General Details

Variable	Respondent	Percentage
Gender		
Male	139	64.4
Female	77	35.6
Total	216	100
Age (years)		

Below 40	75	34.7
40-45	93	43.1
Above 45	48	22.2
Total	216	100
Work experience		
Less than 5	81	37.5
5-8	75	34.7
More than 8	60	27.8
Total	216	100

Table 2 Role and effect of Multiple Intelligence on Students' Achievements

S. No.	Statements	Mean Value	t value	Sig.
1.	MI direct social complexities, control stress, and channel emotions for productive learning	3.21	3.141	0.001
2.	Nurture interpersonal intelligence in secondary-level	3.18	2.709	0.004
3.	Foster flexibility for surviving in a globally interconnected environment	3.12	1.835	0.034
4.	Help to focus on the predictive influence of enthusiasm in learning and attitudes	3.19	2.846	0.002
5.	MI focuses on individual cognitive aptitudes	3.16	2.436	0.008
6.	Encourage mindfulness as a comprehensive path for student growth	3.15	2.246	0.013
7.	Fosters greater understanding of diversity and individuality within the educational environment	3.14	2.116	0.018
8.	Multiple Intelligences lead to a more diverse range of assessment methods	3.13	1.973	0.025
9.	Multiple Intelligences acknowledges the importance of a well-rounded education	3.20	2.999	0.002
10.	Educators can design more personalized and effective learning experiences	3.11	2.289	0.047

Table above is showing different role and effect of Multiple Intelligence on Students' Achievements. The respondent says that MI direct social complexities, control stress, and channel emotions for productive learning with mean value 3.21, Multiple Intelligences acknowledges the importance of a well-rounded education with mean value 3.20, Help to focus on the predictive influence of enthusiasm in learning and attitudes with mean value 3.19 and Nurture interpersonal intelligence in secondary-level with mean value 3.18. The respondent shares that MI focuses on individual cognitive aptitudes with mean value 3.16, Encourage mindfulness as a comprehensive path for student growth with mean value 3.15 and fosters greater understanding of diversity and individuality within the educational environment with mean value 3.14. The respondent also says that Multiple Intelligences lead to a more diverse range of assessment methods with mean value 3.13. Foster flexibility for surviving in a globally interconnected environment with mean value 3.12 and Educators can design more personalized and effective learning experiences with mean value 3.11. The value under significant column for all the statements related to economic analysis is significant with value below 0.05 after applying t test.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the idea of different intelligences significantly affects the academic success of students in India who are enrolled in secondary school. As suggested by Howard Gardner, recognising and addressing the variety of intelligences can promote a more inclusive and successful educational system. Teachers can improve students' learning experiences and overall academic achievement by adapting teaching strategies to account for the variances that pupils demonstrate across multiple intelligences. This strategy promotes a more holistic and individualized approach to education by acknowledging that conventional standardized testing cannot capture the whole spectrum of human potential. A more well-rounded and fruitful educational journey can be achieved by empowering pupils to flourish in the subjects in which they naturally excel. Additionally, it fosters a greater understanding of diversity and individuality within the educational environment, which is essential for raising a generation of students who are not only academically gifted but also emotionally intelligent, adaptable, and able to make meaningful contributions to society. Adopting the concepts of multiple intelligences can play a

significant role in helping India's children have a brighter future as the country's educational system continues to change and face new difficulties? Teachers can enhance the learning process and improve overall academic achievement by adjusting their teaching strategies to accommodate for students' unique abilities and preferences. This strategy encourages a more comprehensive and individualized educational system while simultaneously acknowledging that standardized testing may not fully reflect human potential. Embracing different intelligences produces students who are adaptive, socially conscious, and academically accomplished, positively impacting India's educational system and society at large. The study was conducted to know the role and effect of Multiple Intelligence on Students' Achievements of Students Studying at Secondary Loveland found that MI direct social complexities, control stress, and channel emotions for productive learning, acknowledges the importance of a well-rounded education, help to focus on the predictive influence of enthusiasm in learning and attitudes, Nurture interpersonal intelligence in secondary-level and MI focuses on individual cognitive aptitudes. The study concludes that there is significant effect of Multiple Intelligence on Students' Achievements.

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